

TOP TIPS FOR LEARNING ENGLISH AT HOME

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Annotation.

This article presents different strategies and ways to improve English for learners at home or on their own.

Key words.

Collocations, Skype, techniques, into the mirror, monitor, shadowing, imitating, Actresses, stress.

English is becoming popular language around the world. Even it became global language and so that's why people try to learn this language perfectly. There are a lot of effective ways to improve their English level. But learners always have trouble with learning English at home. It's not so easy for many learners. Learners maybe do not have

any native English speakers in their country. Maybe there are no tourists that they can go and harass, there are no groups where they can go locally where they can go and chat and do English, speak English. A lot of people are not ready to go on Skype and try and find some random English person to chat with. It can be quite hard, especially if they are a little bit shy. In this article, Learners may get some

essential ideas and advice about how they can practice speaking, when they are on their own at home alone.

Here are some crucial ways and essential ideas:

1. Speaking into the mirror.
2. Collocation fun
3. Short audios
4. Actresses that you like
5. To send audio messages

*Speaking into the mirror". This technique is really useful and it is really simple. What I mean by this is that, learners should make it a habit. If they can attach their learning to an existing habit, then it makes it much easier. They must speak their daily life, interests, what they are going to do today, in the future, something like that in front of the mirror. It's a bit like writing their diary at the end of the day, which is also a great way to practise writing. At first it looks so ridiculous but after repetition day by day, they can notice a huge improvement in speaking easily.

*Collocation fun. Collocations are words that are often used together. For example, heavy rain, go out of business, take an exam, pay attention, make an effort, fast food, powerful engine and etc. Collocation fun is where we're going to practise speaking. Using a very common teaching method from really based on the task-based approach to teaching. First of all, you should take a topic, especially a recent topic. For example, science. Then you should get some Collocations and actually learners can use their course book or onto the Internet. Then they should make a sentence with collocation and try to speak. This technique will help to them to activate and practise some of these expressions. It will be great because that preparing the collocations, practising the sentences and then presenting a talk is a really tried and tasted method by many. The reason why I suggest doing this in front of the mirror is that actually there are great benefits of talking to a mirror. Firstly, mirrors do not answer back like people. When you are speaking in the mirror, you can look at your mouth and you can see the kind of movements that you are making. It's also useful for pronunciation. And without any doubt, you can see yourself and monitor yourself.

*Short audios. The short audios are bite-sized chunks, they are so easy to use and your concentration is shorter, for shorter periods of time. They should listen and then speak. For example,

"Hello" (audio)

-Hello(you should say)

Nice to meet you(audio)

Nice to meet you (yours)

I will do my best(audio)

I will do my best(yours)

Goodbye and see you soon(audio)

Goodbye and see you soon(yours)

As you can see, you should also pay attention word stress and also pick out chunks or phrases that you like or sound interesting.

*Actresses that you like.

It is one of the easiest way of how to improve speaking any foreign language. Learners should take their loved musicians or actor, actress. And they should try and do the voice and the whole body and they become that character. They can do that when they are practicing speaking on their own. They probably do not want to do this when they are out and about at the shops or speaking to foreign people. But when they are having fun at home, it can be a great way to practise. By imitating favorite english speaking actor, people can improve their speaking skills.

*To send audio messages.

When learners use Facebook , Telegram, Instagram, WhatsApp, other social media that have a chat facility, they often send text messages. It would be great if learners go a step further. They should send an audio message rather than a written messages. People can do this if they have some friends who maybe speak English or family members. If they do this again and again, it can be quite fun to do. And the great thing about sending audio messages is that it is not like a live phone conversation, where the pressure is thereunder people have time to prepare to think about what they are going to say to record it. If they don't like it, they can delete it, record it again. So sending audio messages is a great way to develop their speaking.

Learners always pay attention such ways that how to develop their speaking skills and strategies. To speak English fluently, they should never give up practice. Practice makes perfect. Not only these ways, but also there are lots of effective ways to improve their English. If learners should do all these strategies, they will get their desire result, without any doubt.

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